

EVALUATION OF LANDSCAPE PLANTS USED IN URBAN HIGHWAYS: THE CASE OF BURSA

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(Received 3rd August 2023; accepted 27th August 2023)

ABSTRACT. In this study, ring roads were divided into four regions, and the planting design of the peripheral roads passing through the central districts and located at important transportation network points of Bursa were evaluated. As a result of evaluations, 73 plant taxons were determined in all regions. The richest regions in terms of plant diversity are in the following order: 1st region between Atatürk Boulevard Junction and Acemler Junction, then the 3rd zone between Acemler connection Junction and Mudanya Boulevard, and the 2nd region located between Acemler connection Junction and Ankara Road – Bursa ring road connection junction. The 4th region is the region with the least diversity of plants. It has been determined that plant taxons are mostly suitable for road plants, prefer sun and shade, and are generally resistant to ecological conditions. As a result, it will be ensured to enrich the urban to landscape by supporting the design of the non-planted areas with appropriate plant taxon eliminating the deficiencies seen on the roads, and providing effective views to the drivers and pedestrians except the densely planted areas along the route.

Keywords: *urban highways, planting design, road trees, woody plants, Bursa-Türkiye*

INTRODUCTION

Urban roads are one of the important green areas that support the city's image, establish the relationship between nature and people, and contribute to the city's development. A city's roads, streets, and boulevards add aesthetic and functional value to the city and help support the urban ecosystem [1,2,3,4]. Ensuring effective utilization of urban roads for both drivers and pedestrians is possible with proper planting as well as proper planning of transportation networks. Road planting has many functions as linear elements connecting urban open green spaces. It is especially important in ensuring drivers' safety and comfort [1,4,5,6,7].

The designs to be made on the roads should be suitable for the naturalness of the land, construction, and traffic techniques. It is an old and widely used planting approach called “alle” in which two-sided linear plantings are along the road. Other woody and herbaceous species also accompany alle-shaped plantings. Plantings should be carried out by paying attention to characteristics such as emphasizing pedestrian crossings, ensuring safety between the road and pedestrians, reducing the intensity of headlight lamps, separating avenues and streets, etc. [1,2,7].

On the other hand, the selection of plant species in road planting is an important issue and varies according to the width and direction of the road, the buildings around the road, and the height of the buildings. While the plants to be used must be highly ecologically tolerant and resistant to urban ecology, attention should be paid to the relative location of

the plants to the road, planting features, etc. The plants should have a height of at least 5 square meters without branches forming a symmetrical canopy, smooth stems, and long-lived species [7,8,9,10].

It is important to address and evaluate road planting because it both makes important contributions to the urban landscape and has many functions, such as limiting the driver's area of interest, shading the stopped traffic, connecting and separating the places along the road, determining the direction by preventing the confusion of the driver at wide intersections, being an emphasis element, and creating a backdrop for the buildings [3,7,11,12,13]. To provide effective road designs, it is necessary to reveal their current conditions, identify the deficiencies, and produce solutions. This study was conducted from this viewpoint and addresses urban road plantings located on the important transportation network of Bursa – the 4th largest city of Türkiye – and connect the central districts. In line with the design principles, the state of road planting was revealed, and suggestions were made within the framework of the results obtained.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main material of the study is the urban road planting, which is located in the transportation network that passes through the city center of Bursa and connects the provinces of Ankara, Eskişehir, Istanbul, Yalova, İzmir, and Balıkesir. The province of Bursa is located in the south of the Marmara region, between 39° 35'-40° 40' north latitudes and 28° 10'-30° 00' east longitudes. Izmit, Yalova, and Istanbul are located in the north of Bursa, Ankara, Eskişehir, and Kütahya in the south; Balıkesir and Çanakkale provinces are located in the west of Bursa (Fig.1). It is located on a total area of 11,027 km² and has a coastline of 115 km. Although a semi-terrestrial climate type is seen in the inner parts of Bursa, generally mild climate type is dominant. The average temperature is 14.6 °C, the average relative humidity is 68.6%, and the average annual precipitation is 691.9 mm [4, 14]

Within the scope of the study, urban roads were evaluated by dividing them into four regions. These are:

Region 1: The area between Acemler intersection and Atatürk Boulevard intersection,

Region 2: The area between Acemler intersection and Ankara ring road intersection,

Region 3: The area between Acemler intersection and Mudanya Boulevard and

Region 4: The area between Bursa City Square intersection and the Bursa-Yalova ring road intersection. (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Location of Bursa province (Yılmaz, 2019- Original)

Fig. 2. Urban roads addressed in the study (Yilmaz, 2019- Original)

In this study, observation and evaluation methods were used. First of all, data were collected by reviewing the relevant literature. Within the scope of field studies, plant samples were collected by visiting the regions in spring and summer, and visual material was obtained by taking photographs. Later, plant identifications were carried out using different sources [5,14; 30].

The identified taxa were evaluated regarding plant diversity, aesthetic property, and ecological resistance. Plant diversity is considered as genus, family, subspecies and variety distributions, taxonomic groups (Angiospermae - Gymnospermae), and lifespan (tree-brier). Aesthetic properties were evaluated as plant height, form and texture, leaf and flower color, fragrance, accent, and autumn color effect [15, 21, 26, 28, 31; 34].

On the other hand, they were evaluated as ecological resistance (resistance to air pollution, wind, frost, temperature, salt, and drought) and suitability for use as road trees. They were evaluated as 1. not resistant to ecological conditions, 2. moderately resistant, 3. Resistant [4, 14, 33, 35; 37, 42]. Tables and graphics were obtained by comparing the frequency distribution analysis within the SPSS 22 program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant Diversity of the Urban Roads of the City of Bursa

An evaluation of urban roads within the scope of four regions regarding plant diversity reveals 73 species, subspecies, and varieties belonging to 34 families (Table 1). While 58.11% of the detected taxa were natural and 41.89% were exotic species, 29.27% were Gymnospermae (coniferous), and 70.73% were Angiospermae (broadleaf). Regarding life span, 68.29% of the identified taxa were trees and 31.71% were briers.

Table 1. Plant taxa detected on urban roads in the province of Bursa

Families	Taxons
Aceraceae	<i>Acer negundo</i> L., <i>Acer platanoides</i> 'Durummondii' <i>Acer palmatum</i> Thunb., <i>Acer Saccharinum</i> L.
Altingiaceae	<i>Liquidambar orientalis</i> Değirmeni.
Apocynaceae	<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.
Asparagaceae	<i>Cordylone australis</i> (G. Forst.) Endl. <i>Berberis thunbergii</i> 'Atropurpurea Nana'
Berberidaceae	<i>Nandina domestica</i> Thunb., <i>Nandina domestica</i> 'Fire Power'
Betulaceae	<i>Betula pendula</i> Roth.
Bignoniaceae	<i>Catalpa bignonioides</i> Walter
Buxaceae	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> L., <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> 'Rotundifolia'
Caprifoliaceae	<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L., <i>Abelia x grandiflora</i> 'Confetti'
Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus japonicus</i> 'Aurea'
Cupressaceae	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> var. 'Pyramidalis', <i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L. <i>Cupressocyparis leylandi</i> (ABJacks. & Dallim) Dallim., <i>Cupressus macrocarpa</i> 'Goldrest', <i>Cupressus arizonica</i> Greene, <i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> 'Golden Carpet', <i>Juniperus sabina</i> 'Glauc', <i>Juniperus virginiana</i> 'Skyrocket', <i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> Moench, <i>Juniperus sabina</i> Sm., <i>Platycladus orientalis</i> (L.) Franco, <i>Thuja plicata don ex don</i>
Cypraceae	<i>Carex oshimensis</i> 'Evergold'
Fabaceae	<i>Albizia julibrissin</i> Durazz.
Fagaceae	<i>Quercus robur</i> 'Fasticata', <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> L.
Hippocastanaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L.
Lamiaceae	<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> Mill., <i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> 'Prostratus'
Lauraceae	<i>Laurus nobilis</i> L., <i>Laurus nobilis</i> 'Pyramidalis'
Leguminosae	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> 'Umbraculifera', <i>Albizia julibrissin</i> Durazz., <i>Cercis siliquastrum</i> L.
Lythraceae	<i>Lagerstromia indica</i> L.
Manoliaceae	<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> 'Tige', <i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> L.
Moraceae	<i>Ficus carica</i> L.
Myrtaceae	<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (Curtis) Skeels
Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L., <i>Ligustrum ionandrum</i> Diels, <i>Ligustrum japonicum</i> Thunb., <i>Forsythia x intermedia</i> Zabel
Palmaceae	<i>Chamaerops exelca</i> Thunb.
Pinaceae	<i>Cedrus deodara</i> 'Aurea', <i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb. Eski D. Don) G. Don., <i>Abies nordmanniana</i> (Steven)Spach., <i>Picea abies</i> (L.) H. Karst. , <i>Picea Orientalis</i> (L.)bPeterm. , <i>Picea pungens</i> Engelm., <i>Picea pungens</i> 'Glauc', <i>Pinus nigra</i> J.F.Arnold, <i>Pinus pinea</i> L.
Pittosporaceae	<i>Pittosporum tobira</i> 'Nana'
Platanaceae	<i>Platanus orientalis</i> L.
Poaceae	<i>Cortaderia selloana</i> 'Pumila', <i>Cortaderia selloana</i> (Schult. & Schult. F.) Asch. Ve Graebn.
Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i> Ehrh., <i>Prunus seruolata</i> 'Kanzan', <i>Rosa</i> sp., <i>Photinia x fraseri</i> 'Red Robin', <i>Pyracantha coccinea</i> M. Roem., <i>Cydonia oblonga</i>
Salicaceae	<i>Salix alba</i> L.
Sapindaceae	<i>Acer negundo</i> L., <i>Acer campestre</i> L., <i>Acer Saccharinum</i> L., <i>Acer platanoides</i> 'Crimson King', <i>Acer platanoides</i> L.
Taxaceae	<i>Taxus baccata</i> L.
Tiliaceae	<i>Tilia tomentosa</i> Moench
Xanthorrhoeaceae	<i>Phormium tenax</i> 'Variegatum'

An evaluation of the genus, species, subspecies, and variety distributions according to the families of the detected plants shows that the greatest number of genera was found in Rosaceae with 9.62% and Pinaceae families with 7.69%. In comparison, the greatest number of species were found in Cupressaceae with 15% and Pinaceae with 11.25%. The least number of species was found in the families Betulaceae, Celastraceae, Cypraceae, Hippocastanaceae, Lamiaceae, Lauraceae, Lythraceae, Palmaceae, Pittosporaceae, Platanaceae, Poaceae, Salicaceae, Taxaceae, and Tiliaceae with 2.44%. In terms of subspecies and varieties, the study determined that there were no subspecies and varieties in the families of Aceraceae, Betulaceae, Hippocastanaceae, Lamiaceae, Lauraceae, Lythraceae, Oleaceae, Palmaceae, Platanaceae, Salicaceae, Taxaceae, and Tiliaceae (Table 2).

Table 2. Family, genus, and species distributions of plant taxa

Families	Genus, distribution (%)	Species distribution (%)	Subspecies and variety distribution (%)
Aceraceae	1,92	5,00	3,70
Altingiaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Apocynaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Asparagaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Berberidaceae	3,85	3,75	7,41
Betulaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Bignoniaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Buxaceae	1,92	2,50	3,70
Caprifoliaceae	3,85	2,50	3,70
Celastraceae	1,92	1,25	3,70
Cupressaceae	5,77	15,00	22,22
Cypraceae	1,92	1,25	3,70
Fabaceae	3,85	2,50	3,70
Fagaceae	3,85	2,50	3,70
Hippocastanaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Lamiaceae	3,85	2,50	3,70
Lauraceae	1,92	2,50	3,70
Leguminosae	5,77	3,75	3,70
Lythraceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Manoliaceae	1,92	2,50	3,70
Moraceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Myrtaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Oleaceae	5,77	5,00	0,00
Palmaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Pinaceae	7,69	11,25	7,41
Pittosporaceae	1,92	1,25	3,70
Platanaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Poaceae	1,92	2,50	3,70
Rosaceae	9,62	7,50	7,41
Salicaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Sapindaceae	1,92	6,25	3,70
Taxaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Tiliaceae	1,92	1,25	0,00
Xanthorrhoeaceae	1,92	1,25	3,70

Aesthetic Properties of Bursa Urban Road Planting

Road plantings in four regions were evaluated in terms of their aesthetic properties and are given in Table 3. Accordingly, while 70.27% – the majority – of the identified taxa were between 0-20 m, it was followed by 27.03% of plant taxa with a length of 20-40 m and 2.70% of plant taxa of 40 m and above. Regarding form characteristics, round-spherical taxa were used with the highest rate at 59.46%, pyramidal-column taxa at 25.68%, spreading at 12.16%, and pendulous form with 2.70% was determined. In terms of texture, 56.76% are fine-textured, and 43.24% coarse-textured taxa (Fig.3).

Fig. 3. Distribution of taxa according to form and texture characteristics

On the other hand, in terms of leaf colors, the use of light and dark green color tones (64.86%) was observed, while red-green (12.16%), gray-green (5.41%), and yellow-green (9.46%) taxa such as *Nandina domestica*, *Lavandula angustifolia*, *Euonymus japonicus* 'Aurea' were also found. In terms of flower colors, the use of white-flowered taxa (*Magnolia grandiflora* L., *Aesculus hippocastanum* L., *Robinia pseudoacacia* 'Umbraculifera') was frequent with 26.92% and also creamy white taxa were used with 15.38%, cream-colored taxa with 15.38%, and taxa with red flowers were used with 9.62. Also, the study determined that taxa with an odor effect (14.86%) and autumn coloration effect (29.73%) were not used much, while taxa with an accent effect (60.81%) were found to be used more intensively (Table 3).

Table 3. Aesthetic properties of taxa used on urban roads

Taxons	Plant height	Form	Texture	Color		Fragrance effect +/-	Accent +/-	Autumn color effect +/-
				Leaf	Flower			
<i>Abelia x grandiflora</i> 'Confetti'	0,20-0,50 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Red-yellow	White	+	+	+
<i>Abies nordmanniana</i> (Steven) Spach	20-30 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Green	-	-	+	-
<i>Acer campestre</i> L.	10-15m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Dark green	Light green	-	+	+
<i>Acer negundo</i> L.	15-20m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Light Green	Different colors	-	+	+
<i>Acer palmatum</i> Thunb.	5-6m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Red-green	Red	-	+	+
<i>Acer platanoides</i> 'Durummondii'	10-15 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Red	-	+	+
<i>Acer platanoides</i> 'Crimson King'	9-12 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Red-green	Cream	-	+	+
<i>Acer platanoides</i> L.	20-30 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Cream	-	+	+
<i>Acer saccharinum</i> L.	30-40m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Light green	Red	-	+	+
<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L.	20-25m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Red	-	+	+
<i>Albizia julibrissin</i> Durazz.	10-12m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Green	Pink	-	+	-
<i>Berberis thunbergii</i> 'Atropurpurea Nana'	1-1.5m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Red	Yellow	-	+	+
<i>Betula pendula</i> Roth.	25-30m	Pendulous	Rough	Dark green	Creamy-green	-	+	+
<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> 'Rotundifolia'	0,50-0,60 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Dark green	White	-	-	-
<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> L.	2- 3,5m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Dark green	White	-	-	-
<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (Curtis) Skeels	2-3 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Green	Red	-	+	-
<i>Carex oshimensis</i> 'Evergold'	0,15-0,25	Spreading	Fine	Yellow-green	Creamy-white	-	-	-
<i>Catalpa bignonioides</i> Walter	10-15 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Light green	White	-	-	+
<i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb. Eski D.Don) G.Don	40-50m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Green	-	-	+	-
<i>Cedrus deodara</i> 'Aurea'	30-40 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Yellow-green	-	-	+	-
<i>Cercis siliquastrum</i> L.	3-5 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Different color	-	+	-
<i>Chamaerops exelca</i> Thunb.	3-6 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Green	Creamy	-	+	-
<i>Cordyline australis</i> (G.Forst.) Endl.	1.5-2 m	Spreading	Fine	Green	Creamy	-	+	-
<i>Cortaderia selloana</i> 'Pumila'	1-2 m	Spreading	Fine	Green	Creamy- white	-	+	-
<i>Cupressus arizonica</i> Greene	15-20m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Blue-green	-	-	+	-
<i>Cupressus macrocarpa</i> 'Goldrest'	10-15m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Yellow-green	-	+	+	-
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L.	20-30 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Grey-green	-	-	-	-
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> var. 'Pyramidalis'	25-30 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Grey-green	-	-	+	-
<i>Cupressocyparis leylandii</i> (ABJacks. &Dallim) Dallim.	20-25 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Green	-	-	-	-
<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	3-5 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Pink	-	+	-
<i>Euonymus japonicus</i> 'Aurea'	2,5-3 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Yellow-green	Creamy	-	-	-
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> L.	2,5-3,5 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Creamy-white	-	-	+
<i>Ficus carica</i> L.	7-10 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	-	-	-	-
<i>Forsythia x intermedia</i> Zabel	2,5-3 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Yellow-green	Yellow	-	+	-
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L.	12-18 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Green	Creamy-white	-	-	-
<i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> 'Golden Carpet'	0,10-0,25m	Spreading	Fine	Yellow-green	-	-	-	-
<i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> Moench	1-1.5m	Spreading	Fine	Dark green	-	-	-	-
<i>Juniperus sabina</i> 'Glaucua'	1.5-2 m	Spreading	Fine	Blue green	-	-	-	-
<i>Juniperus sabina</i> L.	3-4 m	Spreading	Fine	Green	-	-	-	-
<i>Juniperus virginiana</i> 'Skyrocket'	4-6 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Dark green	-	-	-	-
<i>Lagerstromia indica</i> L.	6-7 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Pink-white	-	+	-
<i>Laurus nobilis</i> 'Pyramidalis'	7-18 M	Pyramidal-Column	Rough	Dark green	Yellow	+	-	-
<i>Laurus nobilis</i> L.	0-10 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Dark green	Yellow	+	-	-
<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> Değirmeni.	0,50-1 m	Spreading	Fine	Grey-green	Lilac-purple	+	-	-
<i>Ligustrum ionandrum</i> Diels	1,30-1,50 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Dark green	White	-	-	-
<i>Ligustrum japonicum</i> Thunb.	0-3 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Dark green	White	-	-	-

<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> ‘Tige’	30-40m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Dark green	White	+	+	-
<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> L.	20-30 m	Pyramidal-Column	Rough	Dark green	White	+	+	-
<i>Nandina domestica</i> ‘Fire Power’	0,50-0,60 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Red-green	Creamy	-	+	+
<i>Nandina domestica</i> Thunb.	2-5 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Red-green	Creamy	-	+	+
<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	2-5 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Different color	-	+	-
<i>Phormium tenax</i> ‘Variegatum’	0,80-1m	Spreading	Fine	Dark green	Red	-	+	-
<i>Photinia x fraseri</i> ‘Red Robin’	1-3 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Red-green	White	-	-	-
<i>Picea orientalis</i> (L.)bPeterm.	30-45 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Dark green	-	-	+	-
<i>Picea pungens</i> ‘Glauca’	30-40 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Blue-green	-	-	+	-
<i>Picea pungens</i> Engelm.	25-30 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Blue-green	-	-	+	-
<i>Pinus nigra</i> J.F.Arnold	20-40m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Dark green	-	-	-	-
<i>Pinus pinea</i> L.	15-20 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Dark green	-	-	-	-
<i>Pittosporum tobira</i> ‘Nana’	1-2 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	White	-	-	-
<i>Platanus orientalis</i> L.	25-30 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Green	-	+	+
<i>Prunus cerasifera</i> Ehrh.	10-12 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	White-pink	-	+	+
<i>Prunus seruolata</i> ‘Kanzan’	5-8 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green-red	Pink	-	+	+
<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i> M. Roem.	3-5 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Dark green	White	-	-	-
<i>Quercus robur</i> ‘Fasticata’	15-20 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Brown	-	-	+
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> ‘Umbraculifera’	4-6 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Dark green	White	-	-	+
<i>Rosa</i> sp.	3-5 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Different color	+	+	+
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	0,25-1 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Grey-green	Purple	+	-	-
<i>Salix alba</i> L.	20-25 m	Pendulous	Fine	Yellow-green	Creamy-white	-	+	-
<i>Taxus baccata</i> L.	15-20 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Dark green	-	-	+	-
<i>Platycladus orientalis</i> (L.) Franco	0,50-1 m	Round-Spherical	Fine	Yellow-green	-	-	+	-
<i>Thuja plicata</i> don ex don	30-40 m	Pyramidal-Column	Fine	Yellow-green	-	-	+	-
<i>Tilia tomentosa</i> Moench	20-35 m	Round-Spherical	Rough	Green	Yellow	+	+	+
<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L.	2-7 m	Round	Rough	Green	White	+	-	-

Fragrance effect - accent effect: expressed as yes (+), no (-) – autumn color effect expressed as effect (+), non-effect

Ecological Resistance of Bursa Urban Road Planting

When the urban road plantings are evaluated in terms of ecological resistance, it has been seen that the ecological resistance of taxa is generally high. While 54.05% of taxa are resistant to heat, 60.81% to wind, 81.08% to air pollution, 66.22% to drought, and 82.43% to frost, salt resistance was determined to be moderate with 27% (Fig. 4). Moreover, 74.32% of the taxa were found to be suitable for road planting. In comparison, 25.68% were found to be unsuitable. *Acer campestre*, *Aesculus hippocastanum*, *Buxus sempervirens*, *Cupressocyparis leylandi*, *Juniperus horizontalis*, etc. species were determined to be resistant to air pollution, frost, and wind; *Juniperus virginiana* ‘Skyrocket’, *Laurus nobilis*, *Nerium oleander*, *Pinus pinea*, etc. species to temperature and drought, and *Cortaderia selloana*, *Ligustrum japonicum*, *Magnolia grandiflora*, etc. species showed high resistance to salt (Table 4).

Fig. 4. Distribution of ecological resistance of plant taxa

Table 4. Aesthetic properties of taxa used on urban roads

Taxons	Air pollution			Wind			Frost			Heat			Salt			Drought		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
<i>Abelia x grandiflora</i> 'Confetti'			*			*			*	*			*		*			
<i>Abies nordmanniana</i> (Steven)Spach	*					*			*	*			*		*			
<i>Acer campestre</i> L.			*			*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Acer negundo</i> L.		*		*		*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Acer palmatum</i> Thunb.			*	*		*		*	*			*			*			+
<i>Acer platanoides</i> 'Durummond'			*			*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Acer platanoides</i> 'Crimson King'			*	*		*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Acer platanoides</i> L.			*			*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Acer saccharinum</i> L.			*			*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L.			*			*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Albizia julibrissin</i> Durazz.		*		*		*		*	*			*	*		*			*
<i>Berberis thunbergii</i> 'Atropurpurea Nana'			*			*			*	*			*		*			*
<i>Betula pendula</i> Roth.			*			*			*	*		*	*		*			*
<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> 'Rotundifolia'			*			*			*	*		*	*		*			*
<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> L.			*			*			*	*		*	*		*			*
<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (Curtis) Skeels			*		*	*			*	*		*	*		*			*
<i>Carex oshimensis</i> 'Evergold'		*		*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Catalpa bignonioides</i> Walter			*	*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb. Eski D.Don)G.Don	*			*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cedrus deodara</i> 'Aurea'	*			*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cercis siliquastrum</i> L.	*			*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Chamaerops exelca</i> Thunb.			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cordyline australis</i> (G.Forst.) Endl.			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cortaderia selloana</i> 'Pumila'			*	*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cupressus arizonica</i> Greene			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cupressus macrocarpa</i> 'Goldrest'			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*		*	*
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L.			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> var. 'Pyramidalis'			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cupressocyparis leylandi</i> (ABJacks. &Dallim) Dallim.			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Euonymus japonicus</i> 'Aurea'		*		*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> L.	*			*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Ficus carica</i> L.			*	*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Forsythia x intermedia</i> Zabel			*	*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L.			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> 'Golden Carpet'			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> Moench			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Juniperus sabina</i> 'Glauca'			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Juniperus sabina</i> L.			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Juniperus virginiana</i> 'Skyrocket'			*		*	*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Lagerstromia indica</i> L.			*	*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Laurus nobilis</i> 'Pyramidalis'			*	*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*
<i>Laurus nobilis</i> L.			*	*		*		*	*		*	*	*		*			*

<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> Değirmeni.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Ligustrum ionandrum</i> Diels	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Ligustrum japonicum</i> Thunb.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> ‘Tige’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> L.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Nandina domestica</i> ‘Fire Power’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Nandina domestica</i> Thunb.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Phormium tenax</i> ‘Variegatum’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Photinia x fraseri</i> ‘Red Robin’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Picea orientalis</i> (L.)bPeterm.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Picea pungens</i> ‘Glauca’	*	*	*	*	*	*	+
<i>Picea pungens</i> Engelm.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Pinus nigra</i> J.F.Arnold	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Pinus pinea</i> L.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Pittosporum tobira</i> ‘Nana’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Platanus orientalis</i> L.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Prunus cerasifera</i> Ehrh.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Prunus seruulata</i> ‘Kanzan’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i> M. Roem.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Quercus robur</i> ‘Fasticata’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> ‘Umbraculifera’	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Rosa</i> sp.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Salix alba</i> L.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Taxus baccata</i> L.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Platycladus orientalis</i> (L.) Franco	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Thuja plicata</i> don ex don	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Tilia tomentosa</i> Moench	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Ecological resistance: expressed as 1. Not resistant, 2. Moderately resistant, 3. Resistant

Depending on the development of cities with urbanization, the transportation network is gaining more importance day by day. Roads should be strengthened with effective designs in terms of aesthetic and functional value as an indicator of development. Effective designs will be created by planting the roads appropriately and correctly and by doing that, the lack of green space in the city will be eliminated to a large extent and the city will be given an identity. In this direction, observations within the study revealed that there is a rich plant diversity with 80 species belonging to 34 families, 27 subspecies, and varieties in Bursa urban road planting. While planting within a composition was determined in the 1st and 2nd regions, the study concluded that the unplanted areas were more and did not show continuity in the 3rd and 4th regions. Tree species were widely used in all regions. While the brier species are sufficient in the 1st and 2nd regions, they are insufficient in the 3rd and 4th regions. Tree species used were mostly *Aesculus hippocastanum*, *Cupressus sempervirens*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Magnolia grandiflora*, *Platanus orientalis*, *Robinia pseudoacacia* ‘Umbraculifera’, and *Tilia tomentosa* and brier species were mostly *Berberis thunbergii* ‘Atropurpurea Nana’, *Buxus sempervirens*, *Euonymus japonicus* ‘Aurea’, *Juniperus horizontalis*, *Juniperus sabina*, *Pittosporum tobira* ‘Nana’, and *Pyracantha coccinea*. *Cupressocyparis leylandii*, *Viburnum tinus*, *Photinia red Photinia x fraseri* ‘Red Robin’, etc. taxa are used along the edges of the light rail system, separate the rail system from the road, connect all regions, pass underground in certain parts, pass through the middle of the road in certain parts, and provide

smoothing and guidance for drivers. On the other hand, although they differ according to the regions, there is the use of herbaceous species (*Tulipa* sp., *Antirrhinum* sp., *Tagetes* sp., *Primula* sp., *Vinca* sp., etc.), and the study determined that these species are often used in groups under trees or in different compositions such as creating patterns. While the use of herbaceous species is common in the 1st and 2nd Regions, it is less common in the 3rd and 4th regions (Table 5).

Table 5. Distribution of plant diversity by regions

Regions	Angiospermae (%)	Gymnospermae (%)	Tree (%)	Shrubs (%)
1 st Region (The area between Acemler intersection and Atatürk Boulevard intersection)	70.73	29.27	68.29	31.71
2 nd Region (The area between Acemler intersection and Ankara ring road intersection)	74.00	26.00	62.00	38.00
3 rd Region (The area between Acemler intersection and Mudanya Boulevard)	69.23	30.77	71.79	28.21
4 th Region (The area between Bursa City Square intersection and Bursa-Yalova ring road intersection)	68.57	31.43	71.43	28.57

We exhibited that green leaf color and white flowered taxa are dominant, while in terms of aesthetics, generally, there are taxa with a height of 0-20 m, round-spherical form, and fine texture. The study determined that the use of taxa with autumn color effect and odor effect is less in road plantings, including taxa with red, blue-green, and gray-green leaf color and taxa with cream and red flowers. However, while the taxa used in road plantings are highly resistant to drought, frost, temperature, wind, and air pollution, it has been observed that they are moderately resistant to salt. Similarly, Torun [43] stated that it is necessary to use plants in composition in boulevards, streets, and central refuges. In contrast, Ekmekçi [38], Türkdöğdu [13], and Şengül [3] stated that road planting should provide aesthetic and functional effects; they emphasized that it is important to support roads in this direction and indicated that road afforestation creates a visual effect as a whole and improve the urban climate. Also, in their different studies, Lorzini et al. [39], Akdeniz et al. [4], and Zencirkıran and Akdeniz [14] found that the *Itosporum tobira* species has versatile resistance in urban environments. They emphasized that species such as *Acer campestre*, *Robinio pseudoacacia*, *Ligustrum ovalifolium*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Eleagnus pungens*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Quercus ilex*, *Cupressosypris leylandii*, *Platanus orientalis*, *Nerium oleander*, *Acer negundo* are resistant to frost, wind, air pollution, and drought.

Moreover, there are some negativities, such as maintenance and application errors in road planting. That is, although it was observed that the intersections where the planting on the bridges, connection points, and side slopes were at a sufficient level, and the intersections were emphasized in the 1st and 2nd regions, the study determined that there were deficiencies and gaps in the 3rd and 4th regions. In all regions, designs made of side slope stones at some points along the road route stand out, and the mixed planting in these

areas creates complexity. On the other hand, the study determined that the planting intervals of the plants were not taken into account, some plants overflowed towards the pavement, the grid systems were insufficient, and there was physical and mechanical damage to the plants. The study coincides with the studies of Aklıbaşında and Erdoğan [40], Dağistanlıoğlu [30], Türkdoğdu [13], Özgüç [41], and researchers indicated that the crown height should be approximately 3-5 m for the species they studied not to obstruct the viewpoints on different road routes, morphological injuries occurred in the plants as a result of the construction works. It would be appropriate to cover these areas with retaining walls, short plants should be used not to obstruct the view in the roads with curves, and it is important to use accent plants at important points such as intersections. Turna et al. [9] stated that in the afforestation on inner-city roads, insufficient space was left in general. Planting intervals were not paid attention to, while Ertekin and Çorbacı [8] emphasized that the species to be used in the planting of the highways, central refuge should not be oversized. It should not be an obstacle to the vehicles passing by.

CONCLUSION

As a result, although there is a rich diversity of taxa in urban road planting in Bursa, one fact that should not be ignored is that there are some deficiencies in terms of design. It is necessary to reconsider and design the unplanted spaces, especially along the road route, using taxa specific to the territory and region. Moreover, in regions where briars and herbaceous species are used less or not at all, it is necessary to support the area with appropriate taxa, to revise the design in regions where pattern work and slope stones are distracting, to eliminate the deficiencies in the grid system, and to do regular cultural operations such as maintenance and pruning, etc. regularly. On the other hand, although it was observed that the taxa used on the roads have moderate salinity resistance, considering the intensity of the factors that cause salinity in winter, taxa such as *Arbutus unedo*, *Gleditsia triacanthos*, *Quercus ilex*, etc. must also be added to the design. Also, it would be an appropriate approach to carry out effective designs and solutions on the roads in a coordinated manner with relevant professional disciplines, especially landscape architects, institutions, and organizations.

Acknowledgement. This article was produced from the master's thesis titled "Evaluation of Urban Roads in Bursa in Terms of Planting Design Principles."

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